

VALUES OF THE SERUM MARKER OF CARDIAC FIBROSIS AND INFLAMMATION IN THE PROGNOSIS OF PERMANENT ATRIAL FIBRILLATION

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Resume. Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most frequent cardiac arrhythmia (NES), the incidence of which reaches epidemic proportions and continues to grow steadily. The prevalence of AF in the general population is 1-2% and increases from 0.5% at the age of 40-50 years to 5-15% at the age of 80 years. There are various reasons predisposing to the development of AF, BUT arterial hypertension (AH) due to its high prevalence is recognized as the main risk factor for the development of AF. At the same time, in 3-30% of cases, AF occurs without clinical and echocardiographic signs of cardiopulmonary pathology, which is commonly called "idiopathic". It should be recognized that AF is an important medical and social problem associated not only with a decrease in the quality of life of patients, but also an increase in the risk of stroke and overall mortality. The treatment methods used have limited efficacy and safety. All this does not allow us to consider AF as a "benign" arrhythmia. It should be noted that insufficient understanding of the pathophysiological mechanisms of arrhythmia limits the ability of clinicians to predict the occurrence and recurrence of AF.

Atrial fibrillation, cardiac arrhythmia, arterial hypertension, left atrium, ischemic heart disease.

The lack of sufficient data for practitioners about an adequate fulcrum in choosing two competing directions increases the importance of searching for factors contributing to the personalization of therapeutic approaches. According to modern ideas, certain relationships between triggers, substrate and modulating factors are necessary for the occurrence of arrhythmia (B.A. Tatarsky, I.V. Vorobyov, 2005). At the same time, it is the structural remodeling of the left atrium (LP) that has been identified as a key mechanism, where

interstitial fibrosis can be the dominant factor, and inflammation can act as a modifier (AldhoonB.et al., 2010). Since the possibilities of atrial biopsy in clinical practice are very limited, it is important to non-invasive and atraumatic assessment of the degree of structural remodeling of LP using serum markers. The products of collagen synthesis and breakdown (Gluba) are discussed as possible markers of fibrosis in various cardiovascular diseases A.et al., 2012; González A.et al., 2009; Plaksej R. et al., 2009; Querejeta R. Et al., 2004), as well as matrix metalloproteinases and their tissue inhibitors (Collier P.et al., 2011; Huxley R.et al., 2013; Wang W. et al., 2013). As markers of inflammation associated with AF, the most discussed are interleukin-6 (IL-6), tumor necrosis factor - alpha (TNF), C-reactive protein (Strakhova K.V. et al., 2012; Tarasova O.A., 2007; Pellegrino P.L. et al., 2011; Schnabel R. et al., 2009). All this suggests that markers of fibrosis and inflammation may have prognostic significance in relation to the risk of occurrence and chronization of AF, not only in hypertension, but also in patients with minimal structural changes of the heart. The positions outlined above have defined the purpose and objectives of this study.

The purpose of the study. To study serum markers of fibrosis in patients with atrial fibrillation, to determine the possibilities of their predictive value in relation to the risk of occurrence and chronization of arrhythmia.

Materials and methods of research. An open controlled clinical trial was conducted on the basis of the cardiology department of the Perm Regional Clinical Hospital, which included 87 people. The criteria for inclusion in the study were: the presence of recurrent or permanent forms of AF, hypertension of stage 1-11, regardless of the degree of increase in blood pressure. To form more homogeneous groups, exclusion criteria were introduced: age over 70 years; liver disease; chronic kidney disease; pneumofibrosis and severe chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; malignant tumors; connective tissue diseases; patients with an installed pacemaker, cardioverter-defibrillator; coronary heart disease (CHD); cardiomyopathies; valvular heart defects; acute myocarditis; pericarditis; thyroid dysfunction; patients with circulatory insufficiency more than II F. K. KUHN (II A stage according to the classification of Strazhesco N.D. and Vasilenko V.H., 1935) and left ventricular ejection fraction (LV) less than 45%; type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus; secondary (verified) character of hypertension; acute inflammatory diseases or exacerbations of chronic inflammatory diseases within 2 weeks before inclusion in the study. The diagnosis of AF in patients was confirmed by electrocardiography or long-term

ECG monitoring (DM-ECG). The criteria for "idiopathic" AF were the absence of rheumatic heart disease, coronary heart disease, hypertension, cardiomyopathy, pericarditis, thyrotoxicosis, severe heart failure, that is, the absence of obvious structural damage to the heart. (Kushakovsky M.S., 2002). The diagnosis of hypertension (according to the recommendation of the VNOK/RMOAG, 2010) was established after a thorough study of the anamnesis of the disease and examination of the patient to exclude the secondary nature of arterial hypertension. The main group consisted of 45 patients with AF of different etiologies ("idiopathic" AF and AF on the background of hypertension) and 42 patients were included in the comparison group: patients with hypertension without LDC and practically healthy peers (Fig.1). The average age of patients in the main group was 54.5 ± 5.6 years, among them - 19 women (42%) and 26 men (58%). In patients of the comparison group, the average age was 52.2 ± 6.7 years, of which 18 women (43%) and 24 men (57%). Both groups were comparable in gender distribution (Fisher's criterion, $p=0.56$) and age (i-criterion, $p=0.16$). All patients were examined both clinically and using an instrumental complex of methods for assessing the structural and functional state of the myocardium (echocardiography with an extended assessment of LP parameters), DM-ECG with an assessment of heart rate variability, DM-BP, according to indications - treadmill test, coronary angiography. The special complex of examination included quantitative determination of markers of fibrosis (matrix metalloproteinase-9 - MMP-9, TIMP-1, P1SR) and inflammation (FPO-a, IL-6).

The results of the study. The subgroup with "idiopathic" AF included 15 patients aged 45 to 63 years (52.6 ± 4.9 years), including 4 women (27%) and 11 men (73%). The duration of the arrhythmic anamnesis was 5.0 [1.5; 15] years. 3 people had indications of a family history of arrhythmia, 5 people could not trace family aggregation, and 7 people denied the burden of heredity for arrhythmia. Patients with AF on the background of hypertension comprised a subgroup of 30 people aged 42 to 67 years (55.5 ± 5.8 years), among whom there were 15 (50%) men and 15 (50%) women. The duration of AH was 10 [7; 12] years. The duration of the arrhythmic anamnesis was 3.5 [1; 5] years. Familial aggregation of hypertension was observed in 20 (67%) patients, 2 people (7%) had indications of a family history and arrhythmia. According to the recommendations of the RKO, the VA and the ACC for the diagnosis and treatment of AF in 2012, all patients with AF were divided into 2 subgroups: patients with a recurrent form - 35 people (78%) and with a permanent form of AF - 10 people (22%). At the same time, among patients with recurrent AF

(n=35), 12 people had a paroxysmal form (34%) and 23 people (66%) had a persistent form of AF. The group of patients with hypertension without LDC included 30 people aged 36 to 64 years (52.1 ± 7.1 years), among whom there were 18 men (60%) and 12 women (40%). Patients with hypertension without LDC had a shorter disease experience of 5 [4; 8] years versus 10 [7; 12] years in patients with AF on the background of hypertension. Patients with hypertension without LDC and with AF on the background of hypertension were comparable in terms of the degree of increase in blood pressure. Depending on the target organ damage, stage I (2 people; 7%) and stage II GB (28 people; 93%) were observed in the group of patients with hypertension without LDC. In the group with AF on the background of hypertension, all were diagnosed with stage II GB. The group of practically healthy people included 12 people (6 men and 6 women) aged 36 to 59 years on average 52.5 ± 6.0 years, without LDC and clinical signs of cardiovascular diseases. When analyzing fibrosis indicators, it was revealed that groups with "idiopathic" AF, AF on the background of hypertension and hypertension without LDC significantly differed from practically healthy ones only in terms of the level of P1SR. At the same time, its concentration in the blood in these groups was significantly higher than in practically healthy ones ($51 [37; 79]$ ng/ml). The highest concentration of P1SR was determined at AF against the background of AG $130.8 [64.8; 218.4]$ ng/ml. In patients with "idiopathic" AF, the level of P1SR $84 [53; 102]$ ng/ml was significantly lower than in patients with AF on the background of hypertension ($p=0.01$) and hypertension without LDC ($p=0.001$). There were no significant differences between the groups in the concentration of MMP-9 and TIMP-1 ($p>0.5$). An increase in the PICP level in "idiopathic" AF in comparison with healthy ones allows us to assume a possible relationship of this marker with AF. However, the presence of higher concentrations of PICP in AH, even without AF, indicates a significant influence of the AH itself on its level. The literature describes the association of PICP with cardiac fibrosis in hypertension, in the form of an abnormal increase in the level of PICP in the blood in isolated hypertension (Gluba A. et al., 2012; Lopez V. et al., 2005; Macías V. et al., 2012). In "idiopathic" AF, there are data confirming the presence of fibrosis and inflammation in the atrial tissues (Frustaci A. et al., 1997). Analysis of the values of inflammatory markers showed that the highest concentration of TNF- α was determined in patients with hypertension without LDC $2.1 [1.2; 4.8]$ pg/ml, while they significantly differed from its values in practically healthy and patients with "idiopathic" AF ($p=0.02$ and $p=0.03$). And the level of IL- β was

higher than in practically healthy patients only in the groups of patients with hypertension: 2.5 [1.6; 4.8] pg/ml without LDC ($p=0.01$) and 5.6 [2.3; 18.6] pg/ml with AF ($p=0.0005$). Probably, in our study, the markers of inflammation were more correlated with hypertension than with AF. The role of systemic inflammation in the development of hypertension is actively discussed in the literature (Androulakis E. et al., 2011; Montecucco F. et al., 2011; Stefanadi E. et al., 2010). Recent studies show that elevated levels of IL-6 and TNF- α in hypertension are associated with endothelial dysfunction and disease progression (Fang S. et al., 2013; Morillas P. et al., 2012). Although the question remains unresolved whether the inflammation is systemic in AF. It has been proven that higher values of inflammatory markers are recorded at the time of arrhythmia paroxysm (Tarasova O.A., 2007) or when taking blood at the time of an attack of AF from the coronary sinus (Marcus G. et al., 2010). On the basis of which it was established that AF leads to sequestration of inflammatory cytokines in the heart, and perhaps differences in the concentration of cytokines in AF are related to this. It is possible that in our study we are dealing with a similar phenomenon, since most patients with recurrent AF were examined outside of paroxysm. It is important to note that the levels of fibrosis and inflammation markers did not significantly differ between men and women, and did not depend on age. When assessing markers of fibrosis and inflammation depending on the functional class of heart failure, there were no significant differences in FC I and FC II CHF (U-criterion, $p>0.05$). This may be due to the absence of patients with severe circulatory insufficiency (Gaggin P., Januzzi J., 2013). In our study, the dependence of the concentration of fibrosis markers on the form of AF was established. In permanent AF, in comparison with recurrent forms of arrhythmia, lower values of TIMP-1 (521 [473; 712] ng/ml versus 418 [347; 524] ng/ml, $p=0.04$) and, conversely, significantly higher concentrations of PICP (85 [54; 151] ng/ml against 182 [120; 282] ng/ml, $p=0.01$). In comparison with practically healthy patients, there was only an increase in the level of PICP in relapsing and to an even greater extent in permanent AF. Markers of inflammation only tended to increase in permanent AF, without significant significance. The concentration of MMP-9 did not depend on the form.

Conclusion: the hypothesis of our study is that the increased level of serum fibrosis marker - PICP - is associated with structural remodeling of LP and indirectly reflects the degree of degenerative changes in its extracellular matrix. The results obtained made it possible to identify and prove the

predictive significance of fibrosis markers, in combination with echocardiographic parameters in relation to the risk of occurrence and chronization of AF.

Conclusions 1. Atrial fibrillation is accompanied by a change in the level of serum markers of fibrosis, namely the C-terminal propeptide procollagen type I. Its concentration increases with "idiopathic" AF and, to a greater extent, with a combination of arrhythmia with arterial hypertension.

2. The concentration of fibrosis markers depends on the form of AF: the level of the type I procollagen sterminal propeptide increases with recurrent and permanent forms, and with higher values with a constant form.

3. AF is accompanied by structural and functional changes of the atria, which depend on the cause of the arrhythmia and its course. Dilatation of the left atrium in "idiopathic" AF is insignificant, with the combination of AF with hypertension, the size of the left atrium is significantly larger. Patients with a permanent form of AF have a more pronounced degree of dilatation of the left atrium.

4. Serum markers of fibrosis, namely the C-terminal propeptide procollagen are associated with remodeling of the left atrium. The progression of left atrial dilatation is associated with an increase in this indicator.

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